

tration of NH_4^+ in the soil. NH_3 volatilization from NCBU and with uncoated urea was the same.

Irrespective of soil amendment and N source, NH_3 volatilization was less when

N was surface mixed rather than surface applied. This may be because more of the surface area of soil organic matter and clay was available for sorption of NH_4^+ -N ions. □

Fertilizer management—organic sources

Effect of gypsum-enriched biogas sludge and farmyard manure (FYM) on rice yield

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We evaluated the effect of biogas sludge and FYM on rice yields in two successive field trials, Jul-Oct 1989 and Nov-Feb 1990. Rice cultivars were IR20 and ADT37.

Soil of the experimental field the first season was clay loam with pH 7.4; EC 0.6 dS/m; 0.44% organic C; and available N, P_2O_5 , K_2O were 225, 14, 312 kg/ha, respectively. Soil of the experimental field the second season was clay loam with pH 7.2; EC 0.5 dS/m; 0.43% organic C; and 238, 23, 314 kg available N, P_2O_5 , K_2O /ha, respectively.

The biogas sludge contained 1.5% N, 0.82% P_2O_5 , and 0.75% K_2O . FYM

contained 0.85% N, 0.35% P_2O_5 , 0.688 K_2O , and 58% water in season 1, and 0.75% N, 0.61% P_2O_5 , 0.63% K_2O , and 57% water in season 2. In both seasons, N, P_2O_5 , and K_2O at 100, 50, and 50 kg/ha were applied as urea, single superphosphate, and muriate of potash. The experiments were laid out in a randomized block design with three replications (see table for treatments).

Growth and yield attributes and grain and straw yields were favorably influenced by biogas sludge and FYM both seasons. Added gypsum acted as an absorbent, reducing the moisture content of biogas wet sludge and FYM by 30 and 10%, respectively.

Grain yields were highest with enriched biogas sludge both seasons. The next best was enriched FYM. Enrichment of wet biogas sludge with gypsum increased yields 0.95 and 0.71 t/ha in the first and second seasons, respectively. Enriched FYM increased yields 0.67 and 0.56 t/ha. □

Effect of gypsum-enriched biogas sludge and farmyard manure on rice yield.

Treatment	Panicles/m ²		Filled grains/panicle		Grain yield (t/ha)		Straw yield (t/ha)	
	Season 1	Season 2	Season 1	Season 2	Season 1	Season 2	Season 1	Season 2
Biogas wet sludge (10t/ha)	384	354	98	71	7.5	3.7	13.0	4.9
Biogas dried sludge (10t/ha)	385	365	99	71	7.8	3.8	13.7	5.1
Biogas wet sludge (10t/ha) enriched with 250 kg gypsum/ha	413	412	109	74	8.4	4.4	15.3	6.2
FYM (10t/ha)	341	343	99	72	7.3	3.7	12.6	4.8
FYM (10t/ha) enriched with 250 kg gypsum/ha	385	407	107	74	8.0	4.3	14.7	5.8
Gypsum (250 kg/ha)	330	324	107	70	6.8	3.5	11.5	4.7
Control	324	313	97	70	6.6	3.2	11.0	4.6
LSD(0.05)	1	11	2	2	0.2	0.1	0.5	0.2

Fertilizer management— inorganic sources

Effect of irrigation and nitrogen on transplanted summer rice yield and water use efficiency

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We studied the effect of three irrigation schedules and four N levels on grain yield and water use efficiency of transplanted summer rice (Apr-Jul) 1987-89.

The soil was acidic sandy loam (pH 5.4), low in total N (0.065%), medium in available P_2O_5 (18 kg/ha; Bray and Kurtz No.1), and low in available K_2O (86 kg/ha; neutral ammonium acetate method). The rice variety used was IR50. Phosphate and potash were applied at 20 kg each/ha. Average rainfall during the 3 yr was 688 mm.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications. Treatments are given in Table 1.

Irrigation schedule had no effect on grain yield. During the summer season, rainfall increased from the early vegeta-

Table 1. Effect of irrigation schedule and N level on grain yield of summer rice in Assam, India.

Treatment ^a	Grain yield (t/ha)			
	1987	1988	1989	Pooled
Irrigation				
Continuous submergence	2.2	1.4	2.7	2.1
7 cm water 1DADPW	2.0	1.6	2.7	2.1
7 cm water 3DADPW	2.1	1.6	2.8	2.2
LSD(0.05)	ns	0.05	ns	ns
N level (kg/ha)				
0	2.0	1.7	2.2	1.9
40	2.2	1.4	2.7	2.1
80	2.0	1.5	3.0	2.2
120	2.2	1.5	3.1	2.3
LSD(0.05)	ns	ns	0.12	0.14

^a DADPW = days after disappearance of ponded water.